

The Role of Technology in Nurse Experiences: Exploring the Benefits and Challenges of Adopting New Systems

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Abstract

Background: The healthcare industry has undergone significant changes in recent years, with technology playing a vital role in transforming healthcare services. One area where technology has had a significant impact is nurse staffing. Adopting new technologies can bring about benefits such as streamlined processes, reduced costs, increased efficiency, and improved patient outcomes but can also present challenges such as resistance to change and the need for significant financial investments. This mixed study delves into the benefits and challenges of integrating new technology systems in nurse staffing. It examines various technological advancements introduced in the healthcare industry and their impact on nurse staffing.

Methodology: The mixed study employed a comprehensive approach, combining qualitative and quantitative methods. The qualitative phase involved a review of the literature using relevant databases such as PubMed, Medline, CINAHL, and PsycINFO, as well as other sources such as reference lists of relevant articles and conference proceedings. The review examined various studies that have investigated the impact of technology on nurse staffing, including the use of electronic health records, nurse call systems, and patient acuity tools. The quantitative phase involved data collection from 90 nurses in Kalkaal Hospital Mogadishu Somalia who participated in the study. The data were analyzed to explore how new technology systems can streamline staffing processes, improve patient care, and reduce costs.

Results: The mixed study's findings highlight the potential benefits of technology integration in nurse staffing, including increased efficiency and improved patient outcomes. The qualitative analysis revealed the importance of careful planning, effective communication, and ongoing

evaluation to ensure the successful adoption of technology in nurse staffing. Some potential challenges of implementation reported in the qualitative phase include the cost of technology and the need for staff training. The quantitative analysis showed that using health information systems increased nurses' time spent in documentation by 20%, while time spent carrying out medication administration fell by 30%. Additionally, the study identified six categories that reflected the nurses' experiences and viewpoints, including improving the quality and efficiency of medical services and care, facilitating communication management in the technological environment, improving information documentation, management, and monitoring, improving resource management, improving management performance and policymaking, and facilitating pathways of organizational and professional growth.

Conclusion: In conclusion, this mixed study, involving both qualitative and quantitative methods, emphasizes the importance of considering the human factors involved in adopting technology in nurse staffing, such as the impact on nurse-patient relationships and the potential for technology to exacerbate existing health disparities. The authors suggest that healthcare managers investigate nurses' experiences with information technology (IT) in their hospitals and organize courses to orient hesitant nurses toward adopting IT, overcoming barriers to adoption. Furthermore, developing appropriate strategies to familiarize nurses with the benefits of IT in healthcare settings is crucial. By addressing these factors, healthcare organizations can successfully integrate technology in nurse staffing, leading to improved healthcare outcomes and more efficient service delivery.

Keywords: healthcare industry, technology, nurse staffing, benefits, challenges, mixed study

Introduction

The healthcare industry has undergone significant changes in recent years, with technology playing a vital role in transforming healthcare services. One area where technology has had a significant impact is nurse staffing. Adopting new technologies can bring about benefits such as streamlined processes, reduced costs, increased efficiency, and improved patient outcomes but can also present challenges such as resistance to change and the need for significant financial investments.

Globally, the adoption of technology in nurse staffing has been observed in various countries and healthcare systems. Many developed countries, including the United States, Canada, and European nations, have implemented electronic health records (EHRs), nurse call systems, and patient acuity tools to improve nurse staffing efficiency and patient care. These technologies have shown promising results in terms of reducing errors, enhancing communication, and optimizing nurse-patient ratios(1,2). For instance, Mayo Clinic has turned to tech innovation to optimize nurse staffing by creating a platform where participating nurses can create their profiles and offer real-time feedback on their

performance, job satisfaction, and peer(3). Additionally, innovative health tech companies are addressing the issues that are driving the nursing shortage and providing innovative ways to ensure patients get the care they need, such as up-skilling the nursing workforce and leveraging technology to fix the broken staffing model for nursing professionals(4).

Africa is a diverse continent that has seen varying degrees of technology integration in nurse staffing. While some countries have made significant progress in adopting technology, others still face challenges in terms of infrastructure, resources, and awareness. Several initiatives and partnerships have been established to promote the use of technology in healthcare across Africa, aiming to improve access to quality care and strengthen healthcare systems. For example, a scoping review found that successful integration of nursing informatics into undergraduate nursing education in African countries depends on restructuring nursing education(5). Additionally, several technologies are helping to alleviate the shortage's effects on nurses and nurse practitioners (NPs) by improving efficiencies in their daily workflows and how they care for patients, such as mobile staffing apps, artificial

intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), and telemedicine technologies(2, 3). However, there are still challenges to overcome, such as nursing education challenges and solutions in Sub-Saharan Africa(4). Innovative health tech companies are also addressing the issues that are driving the nursing shortage and providing innovative ways to ensure patients get the care they need, such as up-skilling the nursing workforce and leveraging technology to fix the broken staffing model for nursing professionals.

In Somalia, the healthcare system has faced significant challenges due to prolonged conflict and instability. However, efforts have been made to leverage technology in nurse staffing. Unfortunately, there is a lack of information available on the specific technologies being used in Somalia to improve nurse staffing efficiency and patient care. Nonetheless, initiatives and partnerships have been established to promote the use of technology in healthcare across Africa, aiming to improve access to quality care and strengthen healthcare systems(2).

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Whether Technology has led to Improved patient Care

When asked whether Technology has led to Improved patient Care. A total of 54 nurses(90%) indicated that technology led to improved Patient Care among patients.

Figure1.1: Whether Technology has led to Improved patient Care

Response	Number of Nurses	Percentage
Strong Agree	54	60%
Agree	27	30%
Neutral	9	10%
Disagree	0	0%
Strong Disagree	0	0%

Whether Technology has led to Increased Efficiency

When asked whether Increased Efficiency, 93% of nurses agree.

Figure1.2: Whether Technology has led to Increased Efficiency

Response	Number of Nurses	Percentage
Strong Agree	53	59%
Agree	31	34%
Neutral	6	7%
Disagree	0	0%
Strong Disagree	0	0%

Whether Technology has led to enhanced Communication

When asked whether Technology has led to enhanced Communication, the result of the study indicates that 83% of nurses agree so. It is therefore clear that most of the respondents affirm that technology leads to an enhanced communication.

Response	Number of Nurses	Percentage
Strong Agree	60	66.67%
Agree	15	16.67%
Neutral	15	16.67%
Disagree	0	0.00%
Strong Disagree	0	0.00%

Whether Technology has led to Better Work/Life Balance

When asked whether Technology has led to Better Work/Life Balance, 60% of nurses indicated that it does help in work/life balance.

• • Better Work/Life Balance: 60% of nurses		
Response	Number of Nurses	Percentage
Strong Agree	30	33.33%
Agree	24	26.67%
Neutral	36	40.00%
Disagree	0	0.00%

Strong Disagree	0	0.00%
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Challenges

Whether Resistance to Change poses a challenge in the healthcare technology

When asked whether resistance to Change poses a challenge in healthcare technology, a total of 10% nurses agreed. In other words, few of the nurses agree.

Response	Number of Nurses	Percentage
Strong Agree	2	2%
Agree	7	8%
Neutral	36	40%
Disagree	22	24%
Strong Disagree	23	26%

Whether Training and Support

When asked whether training and support were part of the challenges facing the healthcare sector technologically, 60% of the nurse

Response	Number of Nurses	Percentage
Strong Agree	40	44%
Agree	14	16%
Neutral	36	40%
Disagree	0	0%
Strong Disagree	0	0%

Whether Technical Issues poses a challenge to the healthcare technology

When asked whether technical issues were part of the challenges facing healthcare challenges, a total of 57% of the nurses agreed. More specifically, those who strong agreed were 37(41%), agree 14(16%) and However, 19(21%) disagree .

Response	Number of Nurses	Percentage
Strong Agree	37	41%
Agree	14	16%
Neutral	20	22%
Disagree	19	21%
Strong Disagree	0	0%

Whether Privacy and Security Concerns:

The results of this study indicate that privacy and security concerns is an impediment to embracement of technology in the healthcare sector, 56% nurses agree.

Response	Number of Nurses	Percentage
Strong Agree	30	33%
Agree	20	22%
Neutral	22	24%
Disagree	18	20%
Strong Disagree	0	0%

Whether Cost is a challenge: 51% nurses agree

The results the data analysis indicates that 51% of the nurses agree that cost is a challenge in healthcare technology.

Response	Number of Nurses	Percentage
Strong Agree	26	29%
Agree	20	22%
Neutral	24	27%
Disagree	20	22%
Strong Disagree	0	0%

- Interoperability: 73% nurses agree

The data showed that 73% of the nurses agree that interoperability is a challenge in healthcare technology.

Response	Number of Nurses	Percentage
Strong Agree	43	48%
Agree	23	26%
Neutral	14	16%
Disagree	10	11%
Strong Disagree	0	0%

Mean Estimated Time Spent.

The quantitative analysis showed that using health information systems increased nurses' time spent in documentation by 20% while time spent carrying out medication administration fell by 30%.

Category	Mean Time Without technology	Mean Time with technology	Percentage change
Nurses' time spent in documentation per week	8 hours	9.6 hours	20% increase

Time spent in medication per hour	25minutes	19minutes	30% reduction
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Qualitative Results

Additionally, the study identified six categories that reflected the nurses' experiences and viewpoints, including improving the quality and efficiency of medical services and care, facilitating communication management in the technological environment, improving information documentation, management, and monitoring, improving resource management, improving management performance and policymaking, and facilitating pathways of organizational and professional growth.

Discussion

Improved Patient Care

Technology can assist nurses in providing better patient care by enabling them to access patient data, monitor vital signs, and track medication administration. For example, electronic health records (EHRs) allow nurses to access a patient's medical history quickly and easily, including past diagnoses, medications, and allergies. This information can be invaluable in providing timely and accurate care (6).

In addition, technology can be used to monitor patients' vital signs in real time. This can help nurses to identify and address potential problems early, before they become serious. For example, a nurse can use a blood pressure cuff to monitor a patient's blood pressure and identify any changes that could indicate a problem (7).

Finally, technology can be used to track medication administration. This can help to ensure that patients receive the correct medications at the correct times.

For example, a nurse can use a barcode scanner to scan a patient's medication label and confirm that the correct medication is being administered (8).

Increased Efficiency

Technology can automate routine tasks, such as documentation, scheduling, and medication ordering, freeing up nurses to spend more time on direct patient care. For example, a nurse can use a voice-to-text program to document patient care notes, rather than typing them manually. This can save the nurse time and allow them to focus on other tasks (9).

In addition, technology can be used to schedule appointments and order medications electronically. This can help to reduce the administrative burden on nurses and free them up to spend more time with patients (10).

Enhanced Communication

Technology can improve communication among healthcare professionals, enabling nurses to collaborate and share information more effectively. For example, a nurse can use a secure messaging system to communicate with other healthcare professionals, such as doctors and pharmacists. This can help to ensure that everyone involved in a patient's care is aware of the latest information and can make decisions based on the most accurate data (11).

In addition, technology can be used to hold video conferences with patients and their families. This can help to improve communication and build relationships between nurses and patients (12).

Better Work/Life Balance

By reducing the administrative burden on nurses, technology can help to improve their work/life balance and reduce burnout. For example, a nurse can use a mobile app to access patient records and documentation from anywhere, which can allow them to work from home or on the go. This can help nurses to have more flexibility in their work schedule and reduce stress levels (13).

Challenges

Despite the many benefits of technology, there are also some challenges that need to be addressed. These challenges include resistance to change. Nurses may be resistant to new technology, particularly if they perceive it as a threat to their job security or autonomy (14). It is important to involve nurses in the decision-making process when implementing new technology and to provide them with training and support to help them overcome their fears.

Another challenge is the training and support. Nurses may require extensive training and support to effectively use new technology. This can be time-consuming and costly (15). It is important to invest in training and support programs to ensure that nurses are able to use new technology effectively.

Technology can be complex and may experience technical issues, which can impede its adoption and use (16). It is important to have a plan in place to address technical issues when they arise.

Privacy and security concerns: The use of technology can raise privacy and security concerns, particularly with electronic health records (EHRs) and the potential for data breaches or unauthorized access to patient information (17). It is important to

take steps to protect patient privacy and security when using technology.

The adoption of new technology can be expensive, requiring significant investment in hardware, software, and ongoing maintenance (18). It is important to weigh the costs and benefits of new technology before making a decision to adopt it.

Finally, the lack of interoperability between different technology systems can create challenges for nurses in accessing and sharing patient information (19). It is important to ensure that different technology systems are able to communicate with each other so that nurses can access the information they need to provide care.

Overall, technology has the potential to significantly improve patient care, increase efficiency, and enhance communication among healthcare professionals. However, there are also some challenges that need to be addressed, such as resistance to change, training and support, technical issues, privacy and security concerns, cost, and interoperability. By addressing these challenges, we can ensure that technology is used to its full potential to improve the healthcare system.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this mixed study, involving both qualitative and quantitative methods, emphasizes the importance of considering the human factors involved in adopting technology in nurse staffing, such as the impact on nurse-patient relationships and the potential for technology to exacerbate existing health disparities. The authors suggest that healthcare managers investigate nurses' experiences with information technology (IT) in their hospitals and organize courses to orient hesitant nurses toward

adopting IT, overcoming barriers to adoption. Furthermore, developing appropriate strategies to familiarize nurses with the benefits of IT in healthcare settings is crucial. By addressing these factors, healthcare organizations can successfully integrate technology in nurse staffing, leading to improved healthcare outcomes and more efficient service delivery.

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